

Contextualizing Land Administration Issues in Kenya: A Landano Investigation

Christian Koch, Peter Van Garderen, Shadrack Katuu, Barikisa Owusu Ansah

Abstract This paper provides an overview of the development of land administration regulations in Kenya, introduces the Landano project technology, and highlights the benefits to helping rightsholders attain land tenure security.

British colonial law introduced systematic methods for disenfranchising indigenous Kenyan communities in order to transform land from a communally shared resource into a financial asset to be leveraged by the English. Upon transitioning from that colonial rule to an independent state, the transformation of land administration has been hampered by legal, political, sociocultural, and technological challenges; the result of which has been persistent ideological problems within land administration in Kenya. While various Kenyan administrations have attempted to address issues in land governance, solutions have not wholly addressed the concerns of their citizens. The Landano project is researching what land means to these Kenyan communities that are struggling to re-claim their constitutional land rights.

Landano is a decentralized land administration system that is running pilot projects in Ghana and Mozambique. It now has an eye on introducing the same user-centric solution to Kenya. The pilot projects have been informed by on the ground communication with community leaders to develop a holistic understanding of the socio-cultural and regulatory landscape. While system design is informed by local laws and land administration regulations, Landano purposefully designs its solution to accommodate the grassroots needs of local users, each coming to the equation with their own level of education and prosperity. The Landano platform has been developed by international experts in land administration, digital recordkeeping standards, and blockchain technology. The platform creates new opportunities for formerly disenfranchised individuals to own, store, and manage their own land right documents, easily and cheaply. This is delivered in a way that honors traditional relationships between humans and the land they inhabit while also complying with local laws and international standards for land administration and digital recordkeeping.

Index Terms— Kenya, land administration, land tenure, land rights, digital recordkeeping, blockchain, Cardano

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last two centuries, the relationship between land and people has become increasingly influenced by the desire to leverage it for economic development. However, this commodification of land is challenged by historically held perspectives that see the relationship between humans and land within a continuum— one that connects inhabitants to the sacred. In many communities in sub-Saharan Africa, land as a resource is held communally with the intention of leveraging it for more than just personal and economic gain. To that end, individuals living in Kenya are looking to ensure their land tenure and security. This isn't surprising as unregistered lands have historically been targets for predatory development which has resulted in the fear of losing their lands [1]. This is a rational fear, as years of colonization, legislative reform after independence, and an ongoing effort to grapple with land management in Kenya

has revealed a critical need to complete the lands registry system. With the rise of construction projects and displacement of individuals from their traditional homelands, the need to register homes is vital to supporting the rightful owner's claim to land as well as the country's economic development.

Fear of displacement from traditional land and homes has physical and psychological impacts. Studies suggest that increased home ownership rates within communities corresponds with improved long standing health conditions [2]. In this vein, home ownership can be seen as an asset that can empower and develop communities and villages. Promoting formalized land ownership within societies not only ensures healthy communities but also serves as a form of poverty alleviation. Both these identified challenges are in accordance with the United Nations Sustainable Development goals and thus are global priorities to tackle.

Solutions have been proposed to address land security. However, many have either taken a top-down approach or neglected a more complete understanding of the myriad cultural perspectives of stakeholders; in both instances, proposed solutions have not adequately addressed the needs of land rights holders in Kenya. Community members must be included in the designing, planning, and implementation

¹This paper was submitted as research input to the Landano analysis on February 28, 2023. This work was supported in part by the Cardano blockchain's Project Catalyst treasury.

processes involved. Utilizing a bottom-up approach, informed by individuals on-the-ground, ensures social buy-in and interest within their proposed solution. Land administration and registration is a major challenge that includes policies, informal decision-making processes, and legacy systems. These challenges are embodied in Kenya's land management systems.

Developing legislation that allows for the modernization of a land registration system – one which honors cultural perspectives while also creating financial security and economic opportunities – is only one aspect of the work needed to address the current challenges presented in Kenya. Communities need to be involved in the mapping of land, allocation of rights, and standardization of administrative processes. Innovative new technology platforms like Landano, a decentralized land records application, are actively seeking solutions to these issues. The Landano.io platform allows property owners to manage land records for their property via an easy-to-use software application. It has partnered with Digital Earth Africa to make all the cadastral data that Landano generates available for free in its open access geographic information system (GIS). For too long, the processes of generating and storing land records has been opaque and inaccessible to citizens. Landano is leveraging decentralized technologies to create an Africa-focused solution that utilizes blockchain trust anchors to improve transparency and immutability as well as prevent fraud.

This innovative approach to record-keeping allows rights-holders to take advantage of increased transaction security while they continue to seek formal registration for their home and lands. This strategy for introducing Landano's system is revealing. Landano is not attempting to replace the functions of the centralized government registry or force marginalized people to accept euro-centric land systems or norms. Rather, Landano is providing a world-class, user-driven technology platform that enables the continuation and prosperous evolution of the types of traditional land rights practices that have been in place in sub-Saharan Africa for millennia. This is the key distinguishing aspect of the Landano solution that sets it apart from previous, unsuccessful attempts to use blockchain technology for land registration use cases. This paper will provide an overview of Landano's technical infrastructure, current pilot projects, an overview of the development of land administration regulations in Kenya, and outline benefits to ensuring tenure security.

II. LAND ADMINISTRATION IN KENYA

Kenya is an East African country with an incredibly diverse population of over 53 million people that represent many of the continent's major ethno-racial groups including the Bantus, Nilotic, and Cushitic peoples. In fact, the country's most recent population and housing census recognized 45 different ethnicities residing in Kenya [3].

The Bantu-speaking ethnic groups make up about 60%, Nilotic-speaking ethnic groups make up about 30%, Cushitic ethnic groups covering another 9%, and less than 1% of the population consists of citizens of European, Middle Eastern, and Asian descent.

Each of these individual ethnic groups, within broad linguistic groupings, had (and still have) their own unique relationships with land. These are influenced by a variety of factors, including societal traditions, the seasons, or topographic features in the surroundings. Communities from the same ethnic groups can even differ in these relationships; for example, Bantu-speaking ethnic groups living near bodies of water such as rivers, lakes, or the Indian Ocean, differ in how they relate to the land than other Bantu-speaking ethnic groups. This means that while the dominant narrative throughout the Global North has been to focus on the human/land relationship from economic development imperatives, this narrative cannot be considered universal.

Indigenous communities the world over have developed many alternative views of how humans interact with the land they inhabit [4]; the many diverse people groups of Kenya are no different. However, what they have in common is that each of these groups has historically held land communally and allocated resources within the community as needed. This changed with colonization in the 19th century, and the impact of this shift dramatically changed the varied relationships held between humans and land across Kenya.

III. LAND ADMINISTRATION UNDER BRITISH COLONIZATION

Almost immediately after the Imperial British East Africa Company first arrived in Kenya in 1888, the British elite began to seize the land which they assessed as having future economic value. In order to formalize their right to these lands, the British Crown enacted an ordinance in 1902 known as the Registration of Documents CAP 285 [5] which effectively replaced traditional land administration systems with one that favored the colonizers. In 1920, Kenya was annexed as a British Dominion and became known as the Colony and Protectorate of Kenya. More land was taken and reserved for settlers.

With the need to allocate and sell land, additional statutory instruments were enacted to support these processes. Registration of Documents such as immovable properties were made possible through CAP 285 [5] long even before land administration activities such as cadastral mapping were carried. However, cadastral mapping was eventually introduced in order to transform land from communal assets to the statutory freehold for individual ownership. Both the Land Consolidation Act CAP 283 [6] and the Survey Act CAP 299 [7] were enacted for the consolidation of small plots of land, with communal ownership, into larger parcels geared towards economic

activities [18][8].

These legislative instruments influenced land administration policies for almost five decades [8] [9]. The communities that had traditionally lived in what colonizers perceived as high value real estate areas were systematically removed and disenfranchised in favor of settlers from the UK and South Africa— these areas were termed “White Highlands”. This disregard for traditional perspectives on land administration and the denial of other basic freedoms lead to the earliest anti-colonial movements in Kenya. These factors contributed to movements such as the Nandi resistance at the end of the 19th century [10], the Mijikenda resistance of the early 20th century [11], and the Mau Mau resistance of the mid 20th century which was more explicitly influenced by the forced resettlement of communities living within the newly segregated spaces [12]. Eventually, armed conflict resulted in the death of over 100,000 Kenyans and another 1.5 million (almost 20% of the total population) were forced through a system of detention camps and secured villages [13].

IV. KENYAN INDEPENDENCE

Kenya gained its independence from the British in 1963. The new state had to reckon with the challenge of reshaping the land administration system which had been imposed on them. The country wanted a system more closely aligned with traditional understandings of human relationships to land, but also desired to modernize the country to benefit its citizens. Several laws were ratified in an effort to formalize customary rights. Of these, land adjudication was the main land tenure reform carried out after independence and was meant to secure customary rights of indigenous people by issuing land titles [8]. However, many of the existing legal instruments used in this process were still artifacts from colonization and proved unsuccessful in their task.

In 2010 Kenya established a new constitution [14] [15] and it made two significant changes in land administration: first, it decentralized governance across 47 new county governments which were tasked with the responsibility of managing their jurisdictions; second, Article 162(2)(b) established a superior court known as the Environment and Land Court to aid in dealing with the large number of land related legal disputes.

Over the years, a number of other legal instruments were established to help unravel the complexities of Kenyan land rights. However, success has only ever been partial as many of the laws from previous governments still impact the land administration system today [16] [17] [18].

V. BENEFITS TO TENURE SECURITY

What many have seen as merely a technical problem concerning land administration in Kenya has instead been revealed as a highly nuanced issue of varied perspectives, values, and beliefs concerning the relationship between people and the land that they reside on. Because of these myriad perspectives, unilateral attempts to solve the land administration issues through legislative change have at best been inconsistent, at worst they have failed to wholly address the underlying issues and have not resolved tenure issues. Lack of tenure security has a knock-on effect on what individuals do with their assets - whether that's investing in better crops and farm equipment, building new structures, or renovating a family shop. The lack of trustworthy land right records has proven to be the primary barrier preventing impoverished people from improving their financial condition [19]. Proving clear ownership or rights to land through authentic and reliable records has numerous economic advantages. These include safeguarding assets from conflicting claims, the ability to sell one's rights in land, and access to lending opportunities such as mortgages. Mortgage markets are especially important to financial mobility as they allow individuals to gain access to loans by securitizing their real property. This has proven to be one of the primary catalysts associated with economic growth in developed economies all around the world [20].

Trustworthy land right records, like those created and made easily accessible by Landano, provide two major pathways towards economic stability which include increased security of ownership and collateral for a bank loan [21]. Firstly, security of ownership increases the demand for investment in the property. More investment in the property leads to higher output per square acre of the property. This increases the land price and income derived from the property. Second, using land as collateral for a bank loan creates more supply of cheaper long-term and short-term credit opportunities. Longer term loans bolster more investment into the property. While shorter term loans generate more variable input usage. In both circumstances, individuals are able to leverage their formally registered land rights as a means for economic mobility that was previously unavailable to them.

VI. TECHNICAL OVERVIEW OF LANDANO

Blockchain technologies were first implemented in 2009 as the underlying mechanism for the Bitcoin cryptocurrency network. Since then, they have rapidly asserted themselves as a trustless alternative to many legacy record keeping processes which are dependent on a centralized authority [22] [23]. Like a public ledger, blockchains record a series of transactions, the participating entities, timestamps, etc. However, unlike conventional systems for recording transactions, blockchains do not rely on a trusted third-party

intermediary to validate the veracity of the information in its ledger. Instead, innovative (Byzantine fault tolerant) consensus algorithms are used to guarantee the consistency of its data and made available “permissionlessly” and equally to all participants in the network [24] [25].

In blockchain systems, committed transactions are recorded within a sequence of “blocks”. These blocks are a combination of transactional data, with the hash of the previous (parent) block recorded in its header [25]. This allows each block to “point” back to the record of transactions that preceded it and results in the construction of a chain by which the technology earns its name. Because these chains are continuously growing, utilize a consensus mechanism to append new blocks, and each point back to their predecessor with a unique hash, they are considered immutable. In order to alter a transaction after it has been committed, a bad actor that wants to fraudulently manipulate the data needs to gain control of at least 51% of the network. With the rise in the price of cryptocurrency since 2009, the financial cost and risk to pull off such an attack is even beyond the means of nation states. This feature of the blockchain also lends itself to auditability.

While these systems have been, and continue to be, primarily leveraged for enabling decentralized financial transactions, there is global interest in utilizing innovative technologies in other tangentially related fields such as land administration [26] [27]. This is because the land sector, owing to its historically centralized design, especially in the Global South is susceptible to unreliable record keeping practices, the multiple sale of land parcels, and issues tracing ownership [28] all of which are challenges blockchain technologies were designed to address. The incorporation of these technologies into the land sector has the potential to promote sustainable development with reduced risk of fraud as they are secure by design [29].

The Landano project aims to offer a solution to these challenges by creating a trustworthy land record system on top of the Cardano blockchain protocol which can be offered to countries that are struggling to provide secure land tenure rights. Rather than use an environmentally wasteful Proof-of-Work consensus algorithm like Bitcoin, Cardano is a third generation blockchain that implements a much more energy-efficient model called Proof-of-Stake which has an almost non-existent carbon footprint. The project leverages a decentralized record keeping system that creates, archives, and validates land right records by minting them as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs). These tokens are unique digital assets which can be representative of various types of property, whose ownership is embedded in their coding to aid in traceability [30]. The Landano project has ensured that these can be aligned with local cultural practices as well as laws for land administration and digital evidence. The system also provides strong guarantees of authenticity through its compliance with

international standards for record-keeping and decentralized identity.

Landano is not the first with the goal to leverage blockchain for land administration processes; many other projects around the world have attempted and failed to gain traction not only with government partners but with the communities expected to use the technology [31] [32] [33]. The introduction of blockchain-enabled land governance cannot be solely implemented from the top down. Where centralized and traditional governance, forcing a top-down registry approach have failed to adequately meet the needs of its citizens, the Landano strategy instead utilizes a grassroots bottom-up approach. Project development has been informed at every stage by on the ground communication with traditional community leaders – who are responsible for several of the initial land registration steps that their citizens must undergo – and a commitment to research in order to develop a holistic understanding of the socio-cultural and regulatory landscape. While system design is informed by local laws and land administration regulations, Landano has purposefully designed its solution to accommodate end users. This is at the root of what makes Landano different and better.

VII. CURRENT PILOT COMMUNITIES

Landano has been conducting pilot projects in rural Ghana and Mozambique to drive the requirements and design of a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) software release. This is done with the understanding that technology for its own sake is a lost opportunity, and that projects designed and built without first understanding the socio-cultural context in which they will be deployed are inevitably limited in their ability to affect societal change. Development must be informed by an on-the-ground understanding of the people, their culture, and the systems the technology is designed to interact with. This principle has guided activities in Ghana and Mozambique.

After achieving independence from their European colonizers, both Ghana and Mozambique worked to restore the authoritative power of traditional leaders such as village chiefs and family heads. These traditional leaders make decisions on their community’s behalf regarding the use of land within the community. Because of this, citizens of these countries operate within a “pluralistic” legal system which attempts to marry traditional land right practices with the more bureaucratic cadastral systems put in place by their European colonizers.

This has not been an easy integration. Traditional rights all too often fall victim to predatory practices of political and social elites who exercise their control and privilege within the centralized cadastral system and its technology-intensive components. Landano is giving traditional communities a fighting chance by leveling the

playing field. Self-funded through comparatively minimal user-fees, Landano provides its users with a world-class digital recordkeeping system that demonstrates explicit compliance with international standards and national laws. Additionally, the system is designed to be accessed by users with limited literacy or digital experience. The land right records it generates can be leveraged to open up previously inaccessible lending and financial opportunities by safeguarding land right transactions. One of these opportunities being assessed now attempts to connect users to decentralized financial (DeFi) opportunities, such as microfinancing and mortgages, on the Cardano blockchain.

The Landano project is positioning itself to be a globally deployable land administration solution, to bring land tenure security and new financial opportunities wherever they are needed. The project is preparing to expand beyond Ghana and Mozambique into jurisdictions with similar histories and opportunities. This search has highlighted Kenya as a potential future pilot.

Of course, Africa is a rich and complex continent with countries overflowing with many different cultures, languages, and norms. This holds true for land management as well. What may be applicable in one location may not be valid elsewhere, whether in another nation state or in another village. This means that each target country requires a highly nuanced set of land administration strategies that acknowledge and respect the relationships of people and the land, ranging from:

- Cities and urban areas, where active land markets operate on titled land;
- Cities and urban areas, occupied by informal settlements (squatter, illegal or low-cost systems outside the formal or regulatory structures);
- High value agricultural lands which are titled and are part of the formal land market;
- Private untitled lands in rural areas and villages;
- Informal or illegal settlements in rural areas, especially in government forests;
- Lands which are subject to indigenous rights;
- Lands in all categories which are the subject of claims from previously dispossessed persons;
- Government or state lands, reserves and forests [34]

Therefore, it is important to establish a sound understanding of the socio-juridical history of a particular region before attempting to introduce new systems. One of the pilot project deliverables has been to develop a methodology for incorporating these contexts into a jurisdiction/internationalization template which would enable Landano to port this technology into new markets. However, continued development must be informed by an on-the-ground understanding of the unique perspectives held by stakeholders in Kenya if broad system buy-in is to be achieved there. This principle guided the development of Landano in Ghana and Mozambique and will guide its

application to land rights issues in Kenya.

VIII. CONCLUSION

For too long, centralized, top-down approaches have dominated the legal and regulatory environment; this has often been the case in land registration and administrative systems. In Kenya, colonial law enforced systematic methods for disenfranchising indigenous communities in order to transform land from a communally shared resource into a financial asset. Post-colonization, political elites who may have reversed such mechanisms instead profited by embedding them further. The result of which has been persistent ideological problems within land administration.

While the nuanced complexity of Kenya's land administration reveals the need for a different strategy, decentralized, blockchain-based solutions offer exciting possibilities to modernize these systems of record-keeping. This is pertinent for individuals living on the ground seeking opportunities to inform system planning, design, and implementation. Where centralized top-down approaches have failed to wholly address user needs, the Landano approach, used in its pilot project countries such as Ghana and Mozambique, offers value to the diverse cultural landscape in Kenya. Local partnerships and community leader buy-in allows our technology to work for end users by allowing their cultural perspectives to be baked into system architecture. Instead of building systems to replace traditional forms of land administration, Landano partners with communities to manage their resources in a manner respectful of their cultural ideals while also providing access to new financial opportunities and affordable but world-class technology.

Understanding land registration and administrative processes in Kenya can be an arduous task. There is no one-shoe-fits-all approach that will gain long term success, and this has meant failure for many other attempts to address land administration in Kenya. This is problematic as formal land registration can be used as a means to lift communities out of poverty and expand economic opportunities for individual landowners. As there is a push to modernize these processes, sound record-keeping and documentation is vital to the success of ensuring more parcels of land are formally registered in a trustworthy, standards-compliant way.

The Landano project appreciates that this will require significant work. Where other solutions have neglected due diligence, Landano is taking the time to understand what land means to the communities the project seeks to partner with – this sets the stage for meaningful change. Innovative solutions like Landano are piloting projects that are informed and designed by community members and led by a technical team with significant international and enterprise experience. This creates opportunities for

individuals to own, store, and manage their own land-based documents in a way that honors traditional relationships held between humans and the land they inhabit. The result is a record keeping system that provides a type of financial autonomy that is currently unavailable. We expect that Landano's decentralized land record platform will pave a new path towards land tenure security and financial freedom for Kenyans looking for new solutions to these long-standing issues.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tabary, Z. 2018. "One in three fear losing homes in West and Central Africa, poll finds." Thomson Reuters Foundation. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-africa-landrights-lawmaking-idUSKCN1R70JP>.
- [2] Munford, L., Fichera, E., and Sutton, M. 2020. "Is owning your home good for your health? Evidence from exogenous variations in subsidies in England." *Economics and Human Biology*. 39. DOI: 10.1016/j.ehb.2020.100903.
- [3] Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. 2019. Kenya Population and Housing Census Volume IV: Distribution of Population by Socio-Economic Characteristics. Retrieved 28th September, 2022, from https://www.knbs.or.ke/?wpdmp=2019-kenya-population-and-housing-census-volume-iv-distribution-of-population-by-socio-economic-characteristics&wpdmdl=5730&ind=7HRI6KateNzKXCJaxxaHSH1qe6C1M6VHznmVmKGBKgO5qIMXjby1XHM2u_swXdiR
- [4] Sangha, K. K., Le Brocque, A., Costanza, R. & Cadet-James, Y. (2015). Application of capability approach to assess the role of ecosystem services in the well-being of Indigenous Australians. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 4, pp. 445-458.
- [5] Kenya. 1901. Registration of Documents CAP 285. Retrieved 28th September, 2022, from <http://kenyalaw.org:8181/exist/kenyalex/actview.xql?actid=CAP.%20285>
- [6] Kenya. 1959. Land Consolidation Act CAP 283. Retrieved 28th September, 2022, from <http://kenyalaw.org:8181/exist/kenyalex/actview.xql?actid=CAP.%20283>
- [7] Kenya. 1961. Survey Act CAP 299. Retrieved 28th September, 2022, from <http://kenyalaw.org:8181/exist/kenyalex/actview.xql?actid=CAP.%20299>
- [8] Siriba, D. N., Voß, W. and Mulaku, G. C. 2011. The Kenyan Cadastre and Modern Land Administration. *Fachbeitrag*, 136, pp. 177-186.
- [9] Morgan, W. T. W. (1963), The 'white highlands' of Kenya. *The Geographical Journal*, 129, pp. 140-155.
- [10] Gold, A. E. The Nandi in transition: background to Nandi resistance to the British 1895-1906.
- [11] Carrier, N. and Nyamweru, C. Reinventing Africa's national heroes: The case of Mekatilili, a Kenyan popular heroine. *African Affairs*, 115, 461 (2016), 599-620.
- [12] Parsons, Timothy, David Anderson, and Caroline Elkins. *The American Historical Review* 110, no. 4 (2005): 1295-97. <https://doi.org/10.1086/ahr.110.4.1295>.
- [13] Elkins, C. *Imperial Reckoning: The untold story of Britain's Gulag in Kenya*. Macmillan, New York, 2005.
- [14] Boone, C., Dyzenhaus, A., Ouma, S., Owino, J. K., Gateri, C. W., Gargule, A., Klopp, J. & Manji, A. 2016. Land politics under Kenya's new constitution: counties, devolution, and the National Land Commission. Working Paper Series.
- [15] Hofman, D. & Katuu, S. (2022), Law and recordkeeping in four African countries: Botswana, Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. In: NGOEPE, M. (ed.) *Management of digital records in Africa*. Oxon, UK: Routledge, pp. 7-48.
- [16] Karoney, F. (2021a), Interview - Cabinet Secretary Karoney on Ardhisasa and Sectional Property Act. NTV Kenya. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vrrkxdYPgDs>
- [17] Karoney, F. (2021b), Interview - Cabinet Secretary Karoney on Cleaning Kenya's Land Registry Nairobi: SpiceFM. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rj6Hea7SfAM>
- [18] Omondi, D. 2018. Karoney sets up task force to guide on digitisation. <https://www.standardmedia.co.ke/business/article/2001291085/karoney-sets-up-taskforce-to-guide-digitisation>
- [19] De Soto. H. 2000. *The Mystery of Capital: Why Capitalism Triumphs in the West and Fails Everywhere Else*. Bantam Press.
- [20] Rose, I., and Noah. E. 2019. "Ghana: Collateralizing Land Use Rights On Customary Land, Lessons And Challenges For Growing The Mortgage Market." World Bank Conference on Land and Property.
- [21] Ehwi, R., and Asante, L. 2 May 2016. "Ex-Post Analysis of Land Title Registration in Ghana Since 2008 Merger: Accra Lands Commission in Perspective". *SAGE Journals*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016643351>.
- [22] Nakamoto, Satoshi. 2008. "Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System." SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3440802>.
- [23] Lemieux, V. (2017). Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers as Trusted Recordkeeping Systems: An Archival Theoretic Evaluation Framework. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317433591_Blockchain_and_Distributed_Ledgers_as_Trusted_Recordkeeping_Systems_An_Archival-Theoretic-Evaluation-Framework
- [24] Li, Wenzheng, Mingsheng He, and Sang Haiquan. 2021. "An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Applications, Challenges and Future Trends." In , 31-39. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEIEC51955.2021.9463842>.
- [25] Zheng, Zibin, Shaoan Xie, Hongning Dai, Xiangping Chen, and Huaimin Wang. 2017. "An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends." In , 557-64. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigDataCongress.2017.85>
- [26] Augustinus, Clarissa. 2020. "Catalysing Global and Local Social Change in the Land Sector through Technical Innovation by the United Nations and the Global Land Tool Network." *Land Use Policy* 99: 105073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105073>.
- [27] Mintah, K., Baako, Kavaarpoo, G., and Otchere, G. 1 April 2020. "Skin lands in Ghana and application of blockchain technology for acquisition and title registration." *Journal of Property, Planning and Environmental Law*. 12(2), 147-169. DOI:10.1108/JPEL-12-2019-0062.
- [28] Mintah, K., Boateng, F., Baako, K., Gaisie, E., and Otchere, G. 2021. "Blockchain on Stool Land Acquisition: Lessons from Ghana for Strengthening Land Tenure Security Other than Titling." *Land Use Policy*. 109(October), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105635>.
- [29] Khan, Shafaq Naheed, Mohammed Shael, and Munir Majdalawieh. 2019. "Blockchain Technology as a Support Infrastructure in E-Government Evolution at Dubai Economic Department." 124-30. ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3343147.3343164>.
- [30] Rehman, Wajih, Hijab e Zainab, Jaweria Imran, and Narmeen Zakaria Bawany. 2021. "Nfts: Applications and Challenges." In , 1-7. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACIT53391.2021.9677260>.
- [31] Ameyaw, P. D., & De Vries, W. T. (2020). Transparency of land administration and the role of blockchain technology, a four-dimensional framework analysis from the Ghanaian land perspective. *Land*, 9(12), 491.
- [32] Ansah, B. O., Voss, W., Asiama, K. O., & Wuni, I. Y. (2023). A systematic review of the institutional success factors for blockchain-based land administration. *Land Use Policy*, 125, 106473.
- [33] Katuu, S. (2022). Blockchain innovations and the contribution of the intergovernmental organizations. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-07-2022-0179>
- [34] Williamson, I. P. (2000), Best practices for land administration systems in developing countries. International Conference on Land Reform Policy. Jakarta, Indonesia.